

THE POTENTIAL OF KNITTED FABRICS AS A REINFORCEMENT FOR COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Knitted fabrics have been, for a long time, considered to be useless as a reinforcement for polymer composites. This paper will show that the opposite is true: the in-plane mechanical properties are comparable with those of woven fabric composites, the out-of-plane properties (mode I fracture toughness, impact resistance) are superior. Moreover, the knitting loop structure allows for an extensional deformation of the preform; complex composite parts can hence be shaped without major difficulties in one draping operation. This paper will also highlight some novel modelling concepts, developed to predict the mechanical properties of knitted fabric composites.

KEYWORDS: textile composites, knitted fabrics, mechanical properties, modelling

INTRODUCTION

It is very surprising that it took more than 50 years before the composites community discovered the enormous variety of textile techniques. When glass fibres became commercially available in the 30's, their use as reinforcement for polymers remained basically restricted to two forms: unidirectional strands and chopped fibres.

Shortage of supplies of traditional construction materials in the aircraft industry during the second world war, incited engineers to use glass fibre composites in military aircraft. In order to optimise the mechanical properties, new fibre "architectures" like woven, braided, and even knitted fabrics were experimentally produced. The brittle nature of glass fibres required however some difficult adaptations to the existing textile machines. In the early 50's, only weaving remained as a commercially profitable textile technology for glass fibres. The advent of the even more brittle carbon fibres in the 60's would not change this picture.

During the last decade however, the composites community has rediscovered textiles. Two main reasons can be quoted for this.

First, the at that time available "preforms", namely unidirectional prepregs on one hand and chopped strand mats on the other hand, represented two extremes of in-plane mechanical properties, with nothing in between. Moreover, they both suffered from low out-of-plane properties and poor damage tolerance. It was believed that more complex fibre arrangements, as can be achieved in textiles, could help bridging the gap in the in-plane properties and improve out-of-plane properties and damage tolerance.

Second, UD-prepregs and short fibre composites also represent two extremes in production efficiency. Injection moulded short fibre thermoplastics and chopped strand mats are highly efficient techniques from a point of view of labour cost, whereas sprayed short fibre composite products require only a small capital investment. Autoclave techniques, using UD-prepreg, are on the other hand labour intensive and require high capital investments. Hence, the second driving force for the rediscovery of textiles was the pressure to reduce cost, not only of the raw materials and/or preforms, but also of the composite processing itself.

It should be emphasized that the previously drawn picture is schematic and hence might need some amendments. Indeed, woven fabrics have always been present, but were considered as a poor man's alternative for the superior UD-prepregs. Moreover, braidings continued to be used for special, mostly tubular types of applications. And finally, in the space industry, where cost was for a long time a non-issue, handicraft textile techniques (like 3D-"weaving") could be afforded. The real break-through of textile composites can be situated in the late 80's, as can be traced back in conference proceedings (ICCM, SAMPE) and journals, and in the appearance of specialised conferences (like TEXCOMP).

A multitude of textile preforms have found their way to commercial applications during the last decade [1]. New types of weaving and braiding, both two- and three-dimensionally, have been developed; stitching (or sometimes knitting) was used to combine into one package different UD-layers, and eventually to provide some through-the-thickness reinforcement. More recently, embroidery has been rediscovered, in its computer controlled form, as a highly efficient way for applying local reinforcements.

From the family of mass production textile techniques, knitting has been the last to be rediscovered by the composites community. Apart from some rare, isolated exceptions, the first scientific papers, reporting systematic studies on knitted fabric composites, appeared in the early 90's [Ref. 2-10].

The reluctance to use knitted fabrics as a reinforcement for composites was partially based on (false) intuition, partially on (true) facts.

Many composite engineers could not believe that a highly deformable and unstable fibre structure could be used as an effective reinforcement for composites. This intuitive argument was often heard when presenting initial results on knitted fabric composite properties. It overlooks however one of the basic laws in composites: as soon as the matrix is sufficiently stiff to immobilise the fibres, these fibres are fully operational as reinforcement.

A second group of arguments was based on facts. The highly curved nature of the yarns in knitted fabrics will result in mechanical properties which would never exceed those of a quasi-isotropic laminate. Moreover, looping the yarns could result in massive fibre breakage during the knitting process. As shown in Fig. 1, it was hence expected that the in-plane stiffness and strength should be situated somewhere in between those of woven and braided fabrics on one hand, and of (continuous or short fibre) random mats on the other hand.

Fig. 1: Situation of knitted fabric composites in between fibre mats and woven or braided textile composites

The highly deformable nature of knits however raised the expectations that composite structures with very complex shapes could be produced in an efficient way. And finally, nobody had foreseen that knitted fabrics would possess an excellent interlaminar fracture toughness, giving hope for good damage tolerance and impact resistance. As will be shown further on, this has been achieved [5,11-15].

In the following paper, a comprehensive overview of the research on knitted fabrics, both 2D and 3D, at the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven will be presented. Where appropriate, reference will be given to results, available in the open literature, of the few other research groups active in this area.

KNITTED FABRICS

Production of Knitted Fabrics

Knitting for composite applications can be carried out on the same knitting looms on which sweaters, underwear, socks or curtains are knitted. In this way, this composite preforming technique takes advantage of the very advanced level of knitting machinery, which was optimised towards high speed production at zero defect rate.

As for clothing and house interior textiles, two different knitting techniques are used.

In the **weft knitting** technique, one single yarn is fed into the knitting machine. The yarn forms loops by the separate and consecutive movements of the needles. In this way, the knitted fabric is created row by row. The rows are usually called ‘courses’, the columns ‘wales’. The simplest weft knitting structure is the plain weft knit, shown in Fig. 2a, whereas Fig. 2b shows a more complicated weft knit, as used in our studies.

Fig. 2: Plane weft knitted fabric (a) and more complex weft knit used in this study (b)

The needle bar in the weft knitting machines can be either straight (“flat” weft knitting) or it can form a closed circle (“circular” knitting). In the former, the carrier which actuates the needles, moves back and forth, whereas in the latter it simply follows the rotational movement dictated by the circular needle bar. In mechanical knitting machines, basically each type of loop structure requires a specific machine setting; only a limited sequence of loop structures can be mechanically “programmed”, using a cam system. This lack of flexibility has been overcome in computer controlled weft knitting machines, where the needles can be actuated separately in a computer controlled way. This allows a continuous variation of loop structures in both course and wale direction, and even a variation in the external geometry of the knitted product: socks, sweaters or five-fingered gloves can in this way been knitted in one uninterrupted operation. It is evident that this potential has not yet been fully exploited in knitted preforms for composite applications.

An additional advantage of the weft knitting technique are the low set up costs, as only one yarn bobbin is needed. Furthermore, circular knitting is extremely fast because of the rotational, uninterrupted movement of the shuttle.

The **warp knitting** technique is substantially different. A large number of yarns are simultaneously fed into the machine. All the yarns make the same loops. The extent to which one yarn is connected to its neighbours is determined by the movement of a guide bar. Fig. 3a shows a 1-and-1 (tricot) knitted fabric, in which each yarn is only connected to its nearest neighbour yarn. Fig. 3b shows a more complicated structure, as used in this study.

Fig. 3: (a) 1-and-1 tricot (warp) knitted fabric (b) a more complex warp knit used in this study

Already for non-composite applications (e.g. for house interior textiles) warp knitting looms with additional insertion of straight weft and/or warp yarns have been developed. It might be evident that this offers interesting perspectives for composite applications, as the curly nature of the knitted loops can be compensated by the insertion of straight yarns. Although it can be expected that the in-plane mechanical properties of the composite will improve, the price to be paid will be the loss in deformability of the preform and the loss of isotropy.

Fig. 4: Example of a weft inserted warp knit (WIWK)

From this technology, a specific type of knits for composites was developed. In the “weft-inserted-warp-knits” (WIWK), also called “non-crimp fabrics” (Fig. 4), the knitted loops (often out of a polymeric yarn) are only used to hold together the straight inserted yarns. In order to meet the specific requirements for composite applications, special looms have been developed (by a.o. Liba and Malimo). However, this type of knitting generates a kind of stack of UD-layers with different orientations, and hence should be compared with a multi-layered laminate. It will not be discussed further in this paper.

Warp knitting has the advantage over flat weft knitting that it is faster (but normally slower than circular knitting). Moreover, it offers some additional options like the use of more than one guidebar, each controlling one set of yarns, or the use of more than one needle bed. In this way “double” or multi-layered structures can be produced. - The 3D-knitted sandwich structures, discussed at the end of this paper, are a special example of this.- Finally, it has to be pointed out that “jacquard” techniques can be used like in weaving, in order to introduce a specific sequence of knitting loops, resulting in a regular pattern. It is obvious that also this potential has not yet been fully exploited for composite applications.

Although the knitting loops can be extremely complicated, they always follow a repetitive pattern (although the pattern can be distorted during consequent handling of the fabric). Hence, repetitive volume (or better: area) elements (RVE's) can be identified, identical to the unit cells in solid materials crystallography. It is interesting to observe that different knitting structures will have different degrees of symmetry, and that these symmetries can be described in a way identical to symmetries in crystals. Fig. 5 compares the symmetry elements in three knitted structures, with those in a woven fabric. Further on in this paper, it will be shown how the symmetry content of a knit will determine the elastic and strength properties of knitted fabric composites.

Fig. 5: Symmetry elements within knitted fabrics

Processing of Knitted Fabric Composites

Processing of composites comprises three major steps: the impregnation of the fibre bundles or preforms, the shaping or forming, and finally the consolidation (although the sequence of these steps can be altered). In this respect, knitted fabric composites are not different from all other textile based composites. Hence, only some striking differences and important advantages will be highlighted.

The **impregnation** step should be looked at differently for thermoplastic and for thermoset matrices.

Thermoplastic matrices offer the opportunity to be mixed with the reinforcing fibres *before* (using any type of combined yarns) or *during* the knitting operation (using simultaneously reinforcing and TP yarns). The big advantage of this type of pre-impregnated preform is that in principle only one additional processing step would be needed, namely simultaneous shaping and consolidation at elevated temperature of a stack of non-preconsolidated knitted fabrics. Research is ongoing to evaluate whether the resulting product quality can compete with the more conventional two-step process; for flat plates, Ramakrishnan [16] showed that acceptable mechanical properties can be achieved using such a one step process. For complex shaped composite parts, the critical point seems to be the uneven distribution of compressive stresses in a the mould, which leads to different degrees of consolidation. Replacing matched die forming by rubber stamping or diaphragm forming might offer a solution for certain composite products.

In the conventional process, different knitted layers (containing combined yarns) are preconsolidated into “organic sheets”, which are afterwards shaped into the final product geometry . Preconsolidation into organic sheets can also be realised using pure fabrics, i.e. by film stacking; this process can even be carried out continuously, using a double belt press.

The impregnation with *thermosets* is not different from that of other textile preforms. However, one major advantage has to be mentioned. The specific loop structure in knitted fabrics creates a continuous path for the liquid resin during vacuum infiltration or resin transfer moulding. As a consequence, the permeability is higher than for woven fabrics or mats (Fig. 6). In order to have a fair comparison, this permeability should be measured at equal fabric compaction load, because in reality, the knits can be compressed, either under atmospheric pressure in a semi-open mould or as a consequence of higher clamping pressures in a closed mould. This excellent permeability, under any compressive loads, has inspired the Belgian company Syncoglas to develop a unique (and patented) hybrid, sandwich type preform. In this preform, called Multimat, a central knitted layer is stitch-bonded to two outer random mats; the central knit secures the fast resin transport, whereas the random mats provide a smooth and rigid outer surface.

Fig. 6: Comparison of the permeability of knitted and woven fabrics

The **shaping** or **forming** step is intrinsically much easier than in any other composite processing method, because of the excellent deformability of knitted fabrics. This property is the direct consequence of the curled loop structure in knits. In fact, in each loop a certain amount of extensional deformation is built in, as the loops can be stretched. Moreover, shear deformations can be achieved by rotations at the loop intersection points. At these locations, and at high strains, additionally some yarn slippage might occur. All these deformation modes together result in an excellent drapability, which can be evaluated in different ways. Fundamental studies can be carried out on a biaxial tester, which was recently built at K.U.Leuven. (Fig. 7). Any combination of biaxial strains can be realised; the apparatus is further equipped with load cells and a centrally mounted video-microscope, so that the material resistance, and the unit cell deformation can be monitored continuously. Alternatively, deformability tests can be carried out by draping the knitted fabric over a predefined shape (a cylinder with a hemispherical top) during a diaphragm forming process. At identical processing conditions, it was shown that much more difficult shapes could be formed than with woven fabric composites, without wrinkling or tearing.

Fig. 7: Biaxial tester developed at MTM

Finally, the **consolidation phase** is in no way different from that of any other textile based composites, and does not need any further comments.

Mechanical Properties

In the following chapter, the mechanical properties of knitted fabric composites will be discussed. Emphasis will be put on weft and warp knitted glass fibre fabrics (using 68 or 136 tex yarns); - the distinction between weft and warp knits is irrelevant, because it will be shown that the anisotropy in mechanical properties are uniquely controlled by the fibre orientations, and the average properties by the fibre volume fraction and the yarn tex. Hence the way the knitting loops are produced is of secondary importance- . In order to make the comparison reliable, only one epoxy resin has been used (Hexcel F533 in film form) and all specimens have been produced in an autoclave (one hour at 125°C under a pressure of 3 bar). The fibre volume fraction was measured by the matrix burn-off method according to ASTM Standard D2584, or by a simple calculation using the areal density of the knit. The fibre volume fraction varied between 33 and 43 %, the void content between 1 and 5 %.

In-Plane Strength and Stiffness

The in-plane strength and stiffness have been measured by carrying out tensile tests in different orientations relative to the warp (or “course”) direction. Later on, a data reduction method will be presented that calculates the full in-plane compliance matrix based on only tensile test data. Besides, all the strength parameters in the quadratic Tsai-Wu failure criterion can be deduced.

Fig. 8: Typical polar plots of the stiffness and the strength of knitted fabric composites, compared to woven fabric composites and random mat composites

First, the anisotropy is illustrated by directly representing in polar plots the Young's modulus and tensile strength of specimens, tested in different directions relative to the warp direction (Fig. 8). In contradiction to the isotropic random mats on one hand, and a typical orthogonal woven fabric (showing an outspoken weakness in the 45° direction), knitted fabrics seem to have mechanical properties which lay in between those of woven fabric and random mat composites. Moreover, knitted fabric composites can be either highly anisotropic, or almost isotropic. The latter is further outlined in Fig. 9, where the shear moduli and shear strength are represented. It is shown that, in contradiction with the highly anisotropic woven fabrics, which are very weak in warp or weft direction, knitted fabric composites are almost isotropic in shear.

Fig. 9: Typical polar plots of the shear modulus and the shear strength of knitted fabric composites, compared to woven fabric composites and random mat composites.

The degree of anisotropy P_{an} of property P (stiffness or strength) can be represented by the following anisotropy factor:

$$P_{an} = \frac{P_{max} - P_{min}}{2P_{av}} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, an average property P_{av} (stiffness or strength) can be defined as the average over all in-plane orientations. For example,

$$E_{av} = \frac{1}{S_{11,av}} \quad \text{with} \quad S_{11,av} = \frac{13}{8}(3S_{11} + 3S_{22} + 2S_{12} + S_{66}) \quad (2)$$

Similar relations can be written for the average shear modulus and for the average strength.

Recalculating the data from Fig. 8 and 9 would show that, for a similar volume fraction of 40 %, knitted fabric composites can either have a higher or lower average stiffness compared to woven fabric ; the average strength follows a similar trend. It should however be emphasized that woven fabric composites can obtain higher volume fractions at equal compaction , often leading to better average mechanical properties than knitted fabric composites produced at the same compaction load. On the other hand, random mat composites rarely exceed a volume fraction of 30%, and hence the comparison is made (in Fig. 8 and 9) with a 30% mat material. It is clear that knitted fabrics perform much better then initially anticipated. They outperform random mat composites, and they might compensate with their superior drapability the somewhat lower properties in course and wale direction in comparison to woven fabric composites in warp and weft direction. If however the overall average properties are considered, the nearly isotropic nature of most knitted fabric composites outperforms the very low bias direction properties of woven fabric composites. Whereas the degree of anisotropy is strongly dependent on the fibre orientation in the unit cell, and hence on the type of knit, the average properties do not seem to be influenced by it. This is further confirmed in Fig. 10. The average stiffness and strength values for different types of knits at different fibre volume fractions are presented. The fit is remarkable, and even woven fabrics follow the trend. This observation is interesting because knitted fabrics can now be optimised towards other properties (drapability, handleability, isotropy, damage tolerance,...) while the average stiffness and strength will remain unaffected.

Fig. 10: Average stiffness and strength properties as a function of fibre volume fraction

Another concern might be the influence on the mechanical properties, of the deformation of the knit during the shaping and forming step of the composite processing. Preliminary results show however that, if the knitted fabric is not overstretched (leading eventually to fibre failure), the *average* mechanical properties are not basically affected; it is however unclear when the overstretching starts. The degree of anisotropy however will be affected, because the curled yarns will be gradually stretched, altering in this way the fibre orientation distribution. The ultimate anisotropy at maximum stretching will depend on the loop geometry and the biaxiality of the deformation. Studies are under way on a biaxial tester (Fig. 7) to evaluate this phenomenon.

Finally, it can be mentioned that some authors [17,18] have studied the effect of inserted straight yarns. It is obvious that in the direction parallel to these yarns both stiffness and strength will dramatically increase. The practical relevance of knitted fabrics with straight inserts is however limited to those applications where a high degree of anisotropy is requested, and where the extensional deformability in the insertion direction is not needed during the forming operation.

Fracture Toughness

When different layers of knitted fabrics are stacked and pressed, the loops of one layer will intermingle with those of the neighbouring layers. This will be more pronounced as the loop structure is more open, and as the out-of-plane orientation of the yarns is higher. An interlaminar crack will have to follow a very rough path, up and down the intermingling yarns. A straight path is impossible because massive fibre fracture would then have to occur.

As a consequence, it can be expected that the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} (the energy to create a unit area of crack) would be much larger than for unidirectional or woven fabric composites. Tests were carried out [19] using double cantilever beam specimens. Due to the high G_{IC} values and the rather low stiffness of the beams, compared to the conventional UD-specimens, 15 mm thick specimens had to be used. A 3 mm thick knitted fabric composite at the centre was reinforced on both sides with 6 mm thick woven glass-epoxy

laminates. Only then the crack opening displacement could be kept within reasonable limits, and bending damage in the beams could be avoided.

Fig. 11 shows that the mode I fracture toughness is about 10 times higher than for UD-specimens (using the same resin and fibre), and about five times higher than for woven fabric composites. Some other factors, like the yarn count, seem to have an influence on the achievable values. Knit BDD450, having thinner yarns, results in a higher fracture toughness. It was found that the energy absorbing crack deviation mechanism is exploited in a more effective way, because thinner yarns lead to a more tortuous crack path.

Fig. 11: Mode I fracture toughness of knitted fabric E-glass/epoxy composites BDD/450 and BDF/555 (wale direction), compared to wovens and UD's

Similar increases of mode I interlaminar fracture toughness have been found by other authors. Mayer [12] observed in a carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (PEEK) composites an increase by a factor 2.3 when comparing knitted with woven fabrics.

Optimisation of knitted fabrics towards maximum mode I interlaminar fracture toughness is actually being studied. Attempts to measure pure mode II values failed, because the extreme roughness of the crack surfaces would lead to interlocking and early crack arrest.

Impact and Mechanical Properties after Impact

The high interlaminar fracture toughness values of knitted fabrics suggest that the impact resistance might be excellent as well. At least when the initiation and growth of delaminations would control the impact resistance, as in UD- and woven fabric based laminates.

Impact tests have been carried out using an instrumented falling weight impact tester, applying impact energies (“incident kinetic energies”) between 1.5 and 9.2 J per mm plate thickness. Absorbed energy and maximum force were calculated from the measured loads and impactor displacements. Damage was assessed by ultrasonic C-scan and by microscopy on polished cross sections. Compression after impact tests were carried out using a Boeing-type set-up, complemented with anti-buckling guides. The same experimental procedure was applied on woven fabric composites, using the same fibres and matrix.

For the same absorbed energy, the projected damage area (measured by ultrasonic C-scan) was substantially larger in woven than in knitted fabric composites. Optical microscopy indeed showed that delaminations are absent in knitted fabric composites, and that the energy is dissipated in bending cracks at the tension side of the impact specimen. Hence, next to compression, also tensile-after-impact tests should be carried out. The normalised tensile strength of knitted fabric composites does not show a significant reduction, as shown in Fig. 12. This might indicate that most of the fibres do not break at the bending cracks, but rather bridges the cracks. During crack development, the curled fibres in the knitted fabric can slightly be stretched before they become fully loaded. The strong decrease in tensile strength of woven fabric composites is related to fibre fractures around the impacted area.

Fig. 12: Residual tensile strength of knitted and woven fabric composites as a function of damage area

As a conclusion, it can be stated that knitted fabrics are less sensitive to impact than woven fabric composites. Other authors have confirmed these findings [5,11-15].

Fatigue

The fatigue properties of composites based on UD-layers are excellent, mainly because the loads are carried by the highly fatigue resistant fibres. Cracks in off-axis plies gradually degrade the composite and initiate the final fatigue failure.

The slight out-of-plane orientations in woven fabric composites, together with the stress concentrations at the warp-weft cross-over points, reduce their fatigue properties compared to UD-based composites. As both factors are much more pronounced in knitted fabric composites, it could be expected that their fatigue resistance is lower.

Only one source has been found in the open literature [6]. Although only the fatigue properties in warp and weft direction have been compared, both for glass and carbon fibres, the knitted fabrics showed a decrease in number of cycles to failure. Also, the stiffness degradation due to damage development was more pronounced in knitted fabrics. More studies will have to be carried out to confirm these preliminary results.

Analysis and Modelling

It should be possible to explain, and even to predict, the mechanical properties of knitted fabric composites, based on the geometry of the loop structure and the fibre volume fraction, and on the properties of the composing materials.

First, an accurate and appropriate description of the loop structure, and of the yarn orientations within them, should be developed. Second, the stiffness (or compliance) matrix should be analysed, and advantage should be taken of the symmetry elements in the loop structure, because symmetry minimises the number of independent parameters. And finally, predictive models should be developed. It is beyond the scope of this paper to present in detail each of these steps. Over the past four years, researchers at K.U.Leuven have been developing a comprehensive set of solutions of the stated problems. They have been (and will be) published in the open literature, and reference will be given to them where appropriate. In the following, only the major steps in these developments will be highlighted.

Geometrical Analysis

Although for weft knitting, a machine building company has developed software to derive the loop geometry from the machine settings, it has, to our knowledge, not yet been applied to knitted fabrics for composites. If the predictions would be sufficiently accurate, this would be the most appropriate way to determine the fibre orientations in knitted fabric composites.

Up to now, experimental measurement of the yarn orientations is the only solution, but in knitted composites this is a very tedious task. One way would be to map the elliptical cross sections of fibres on a large number of parallel cuts through one unit cell. Numerous problems however arise: 3D-mapping out of a set of 2D images is cumbersome as many similar features (fibres with the same diameter and orientation) have to be followed, the mutual distance between the cuts has to be known accurately... As an alternative, the in-plane orientations are measured on the dry (non-impregnated) fabric. A major assumption has to be valid to justify this (handy) simplification, namely that the in-plane orientations will not be influenced by the consecutive composite processing steps. The out-of-plane orientations are derived from the yarn position at the maximum and minimum height; a linear interpolation in between the extremes results in the required out-of-plane orientation, after a scaling to the actual thickness of one layer of knitted fabric in the composite.

The three-dimensional orientation of a fibre fragment (in itself assumed to be cylindrical) can be described using the two spherical co-ordinate angles θ and ϕ , as defined in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13: Spherical co-ordinates used for the description of the yarn segment orientations

However, the out-of-plane angle varies only between $90 \pm 20^\circ$. For the calculation of certain properties in certain knitted fabric composites, this out-of-plane angle seems to be of less importance, and could hence, as a further simplification, be ignored.

By measuring the 3D co-ordinates of some 200 points along the yarns in one unit cell, the angles θ and ϕ can be calculated for individual fragments along one loop. From this, it is a small step to come up with an orientation distribution graph, as in Fig 14 (the loops have been split up in “straight” segments with an orientation difference of 15°).

Alternatively, a much smaller number of co-ordinates could be measured (about 20), and a cubic spline could be fitted through it.

Fig. 14: In-plane orientation distributions of three types of knitted fabrics

The analysis can be rendered mathematically transparent by introducing the concept of orientation tensors [20], as they are since a long time used in short fibre composites literature. The orientation of each individual fibre fragment, defined by the angles θ and ϕ can be alternatively described by a vector \mathbf{p} , with unit components

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &= \cos(\phi)\sin(\theta) \\ p_2 &= \sin(\phi)\sin(\theta) \\ p_3 &= \cos(\theta) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

An orientation distribution function $\psi(\mathbf{p})$ can now be fitted through the experimentally measured orientation distributions, by the help of orientation tensors of the 2nd, 4th, ... nth order, defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{ij} &= \oint p_i p_j \psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \\ a_{ijkl} &= \oint p_i p_j p_k p_l \psi(\mathbf{p}) d\mathbf{p} \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

It can be shown that these tensors, easily written as 3-by-3 resp. 6-by-6 matrices, are symmetric, and that they contain more zero elements for a higher symmetry order of the unit cell (for a detailed discussion, see [20]).

A complete recovery of the orientation distribution function (ODF) requires tensors with order infinity. However, it can be shown that the nth order orientation tensor contains all information from the ODF which is relevant for the orientation averaging of nth order properties. Elasticity (and strength) are 4th order properties, conductivity, thermal expansion and permeability are 2nd order. The approximation of the distribution of in-plane angles has been reconstructed using the 4th and 2nd order orientation tensors. The result is shown in Fig. 15 for 3 knits.

The orientation tensors can further be used to gain more quantitative appreciation of the symmetry in knitted fabrics. The variation with the in-plane angle ϕ of the individual in-plane components of the orientation tensor is shown in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15: Variation with in-plane angle ϕ of the components of the planar 4th order orientation tensor for different types of knitted fabric

Several minima and maxima in a_{1111} can be observed. It can be proved analytically that in monoclinic systems a_{1111} and a_{2222} must have an extremum at the same angle ϕ . In other words, at right angles to ϕ (min), a maximum must be found. Fig. 15 suggests that BDD and BSS are certainly monoclinic; in BSS, the symmetry axis is however shifted to $\phi=-4^\circ$. This “distortion” can be quantified using a_{1112} and a_{2212} (see ref. [20]).

Analysis of Elastic Constants and Strength Properties

The elastic engineering constants, Young’s moduli, shear moduli and Poisson’s ratios, can be converted into a two- or three-dimensional stiffness matrix. For unidirectional composites, which are in fact transversely isotropic, this is a well known procedure [21]. Only two tensile (0° and 90°) and one shear test are required to fully determine the in-plane stiffness matrix.

If however the degree of symmetry of the knitted fabric unit cell decreases, the question has to be answered how many tests will be required, and which are the best specimen orientations to be used. In a recent publication [22], the authors showed that four independent measurements suffice for monoclinic materials, while for triclinic materials six independent measurements are required. A data reduction method was developed, and an optimisation analysis was made in order to select a set of specimen orientations which should lead to the highest accuracy in the derived stiffness matrix. For instance for monoclinic materials, tensile tests in three directions, in which the Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio are determined (in case of 0° and 90° tests, leading to only 5 independent measurements) seems to be an optimum solution. It has to be emphasised that **no** shear tests are needed in order to calculate the shear related elements of the stiffness matrix. A similar procedure was suggested for triclinic materials, and for the strength parameters.

The orientation tensor approach can further be used to analyse the average stiffness (and strength) of knitted fabric composites. The average stiffness is calculated using the transformation rules for in-plane elastic constants [21], which is slightly more complicated, but also more accurate than the previous one (Eq. 2). Furthermore, it can be shown that the average value for the a_{1111} component of the orientation tensor of monoclinic materials can be calculated in a similar way. If both the average E_{11} and a_{1111} are used as normalising factors, the inverse of the experimentally measured average stiffness E_{11} is linearly related to a_{1111} (Fig. 16a).

Fig. 16: Inverse normalised Young's modulus vs. normalised a_{1111} (a) and evolution of E_{11} and a_{1111} with in-plane angle ϕ (b)

For a specific knit, Fig 16b shows that indeed the Young's modulus for different test orientations follows the same trend as a_{1111} . - It has to be emphasised that E_{11} is derived from the stiffness matrix by a simple transformation of the reference co-ordinate system-. Similar results have been found for the strength parameters, and for the shear modulus.

The practical relevance of these results should not be underestimated. They indeed suggest that the ODF (measured or calculated from machine settings), together with the determination of the fibre volume fraction, should be sufficient to "predict" the Young's modulus in all the other orientations, within a certain class of knitted fabric composites (e.g. glass-epoxy). A similar procedure could be followed for the shear modulus and for the tensile strength.

Modelling of Elastic Constants and Strength Properties

Up to now, only some tools for the analysis of knitted fabric composites have been proposed, and some interesting correlations between components of the orientation tensors and the mechanical properties have been observed. These correlations however have, strictly spoken, no predictive value, as micro-mechanical models should have.

In a micromechanical model, the properties of fibre and matrix are combined with information on the fibre orientations and fibre volume fraction, in order to calculate the mechanical properties of the composite. As an intermediate step, the transversely isotropic properties of the impregnated fibre bundles are calculated first in their own co-ordinate system; then they are converted to the global co-ordinate system of the knitted fabric composite. These steps are identical for all micromechanical models (although different impregnated fibre bundle models are used). The differentiation between the models only occurs in the further modelling steps, namely where the straight impregnated yarn segments are combined with each other and with the pure matrix to form the actual textile composite.

Micromechanical models can broadly be split up in analytical and numerical models.

Analytical models, once implemented in a computer program, in general only require a short computing time compared to numerical models (like FEM-models) of textile composites. Despite their sometimes intricate mathematical formulations, analytical models provide insight in the relative importance of the different geometrical and material parameters.

Fig. 17: Iso-stress and iso-strain predictions of the Young's modulus and the shear modulus of several types of warp knitted fabric composites

The most simple examples of analytical methods are based upon a mechanics of materials approach. The Voigt and Reuss models assume an isostrain or isostress state in the different phases of the composite, and are often used for a first approximate calculation of the elastic properties of UD-composites. For textile composites, these models lead to an over- resp. under-estimation of the elastic properties, as is shown in Fig. 17. Unfortunately, the upper and lower limits are much too far away from each other, so that an accurate estimation of the real elastic properties becomes very doubtful. - It is however interesting to remark that for the glass-fibre epoxy knitted composites studied up to now, the elastic moduli could be fairly precisely “guessed” by making a simple average between the upper and the lower limit; this might however be a pure coincidence.-

In the framework of a modelling study on woven fabric composites, Vandeurzen et. al. [23] have developed a far more sophisticated and accurate position-dependent model, using a complementary energy minimisation technique. It is actually investigated whether this model could also be applied to knitted fabric composites.

More refined analytical models, for which the Voigt-model can be treated as a special case, are based upon the so-called eigenstrain or transformation strain theory. Every yarn segment is replaced by an equivalent inclusion having the same properties as the matrix, but having a non-vanishing eigenstrain defined in such a way that both the original inhomogeneity and the inclusion have the same final stress state. The eigenstrain theory tries to correlate the local perturbation strains to a given eigenstrain distribution. Two problems are related to the use of these models to knitted fabric composites. The first one is dealing with the evaluation of the auto-correlated Eshelby tensors relating the perturbation in a given inclusion to the eigenstrain within the same inclusion. Solutions exist for ellipsoidal shaped inclusions and were originally derived by Eshelby. For curved yarn segments, complex integrations need to be carried out. To overcome this, a short fibre equivalent was introduced. In this approach, the

curved yarn segment is replaced by an ellipsoid having an aspect ratio which is a function of the local yarn curvature.

A second problem arising in the practical application concerns the evaluation of the even more complex interaction Eshelby tensors, relating the perturbation strains and the eigenstrains in different inclusions. These tensors are amongst others a function of the relative orientations and positions of the considered pair of inclusions. Therefore, several averaging schemes were developed taking into account the inter-inclusion interaction in a global sense. The Mori-Tanaka scheme has been widely used in the modelling of short fibre and particle reinforced composites, but is limited to the lower volume fraction range. In the micromechanical description of polycrystalline materials on the other hand, where the volume fraction equals unity, self-consistent averaging schemes were developed. As the yarn volume fraction in knitted fabric composites can be relatively high due to the loose packing of the fibres in the yarns, both methods were compared (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18: Predicted E-moduli and G-moduli using the Mori-Tanaka and a Self-consistent Averaging Scheme

Although these models do not explicitly take into account the relative position of the yarn segments, the predictions are quite acceptable, as is shown in Fig. 18. Further improvements and extensions of these models are under way, and will be published soon.

Numerical models are quite cumbersome for knitted fabric composites, because of the extremely complicated loop geometries that might occur (see above 2). A fully three-dimensional modelling of a real composite (not of simple 1-and-1 structures) would quickly lead to a number of meshes and to degrees of freedom that, even with very powerful computers, are difficult to handle, if not impossible. Moreover, the mesh generation in itself is a difficult task; a mesh generating pre-processor should be in a easy-to-handle parametric format, so that variations in yarn size or cross section, fibre volume fraction, fabric deformation,... could be incorporated without having to restart the mesh generation from scratch. Only if these problems are solved, it seems worthwhile to consider FEM-modelling of knitted fabric composites.

To avoid the previously mentioned problems, the binary model, initially developed by Cox [24] for woven and braided fabric composites, was investigated. In this binary model, the composite is subdivided in one-dimensional spar elements, representing the axial properties of the impregnated yarns, and three-dimensional medium elements, responsible for the transverse and shear properties of the yarns, and for the matrix properties. This model was applied on several of our knitted fabric composites using a homogenisation scheme, in which periodic boundary conditions are applied [25]. The agreement between the binary model predictions of the elastic properties and the experimental values was quite acceptable, except for the shear modulus (Fig. 19). The major problem however is that this binary model excludes an accurate description of the local stress states, and hence cannot be used to predict strength values.

Fig. 19: Experimental Values and FEM-Predictions of E_{11} and n_{12} of 6 types of warp knitted fabric composites

3D-Knits

Over the past ten years, several new concepts for composite sandwich structures have been invented at K.U.Leuven. First, double layer woven fabrics, as used to produce velvet or carpets, have been developed to be used as preform for composite sandwich structures. Second, a similar knitted structure has been investigated. And most recently, patents have been filed for a new, continuous production concept for honeycomb cores.

Woven sandwich fabrics offer three main advantages [26]: first, skin and core can be produced in one single processing step; second, the skins are strongly bonded to the core by the pile fibres, hence preventing skin-core delamination; and third, the core can be easily filled with a foam, creating a (pile) fibre reinforced foam, so that also brittle foams (like phenolics) can be used in structural applications.

As stated earlier, woven fabrics have however one disadvantage: they only deform in shear, and hence draping over complex forms is very difficult. Extending the concept to double layer **knitted** fabrics would solve this problem. Moreover, the knitting process is much more versatile than weaving, allowing to create intricate loop structures and variable pile orientations.

The concept of 3D-knitted fabric composites will be treated in depth in another paper during this conference [27]. In the following, only some aspects will be highlighted.

3D- or double layer knits are produced on a double needle bed Raschel warp knitting loom with minimum 6 (up to 8) guide bars. The skins can be closed (like in 3D-woven fabrics), but the versatility of the knitting process allows one to create a multitude of open skin structures (Fig. 20). After impregnation and curing, a unique open skin sandwich composite can be created. Applications where a flow of liquids or gases (ventilation) is required, can be realised in this way.

Fig. 20: Examples of hexagonal and orthorhombic cell structures

The knitting loop structure is however not so tight as the binding structure in a woven fabric. The piles are not well fixed into the skins, and the skin itself is rather unstable before impregnation. The good binding in 3D-woven fabrics makes it possible that during processing the multi-filament core yarns will stretch themselves, resulting in an open core structure. Due to the loose binding structure, self-stretching of the core is hard to realise in 3D-knitted fabrics. Thick, thermoplastic mono-filament yarns have to be added as pile yarns. If however only mono-filament yarns are used in the core, the resin will not well adhere to them, and a weak composite core is formed.

The optimum 3D-knitted fabric has now the following composition: a combination of multi-filament polymer and glass (or any other reinforcing fibre) yarns in the skins, and a combination of a mono-filament and any multi-filament yarn (polymer, glass, ...) in the core. Impregnation will then be homogeneous. The mechanical properties can be controlled by the amount of reinforcing fibres in both skin and core, by the areal density of the skins (the “openness” of the skins) and by the pile density in the core.

Each application requires an optimisation of these different parameters, which is enabled by the versatility of the knitting process. For an application where a high bending stiffness and an optimum ventilation is required, combined with a light weight, several 3D-knits were developed, impregnated and cured, and tested in bending. The results are shown in Fig. 21.

The bending stiffness can obviously be increased by adding glass fibres to the skins and by improving the impregnation homogeneity.

Fig. 21: Flexural stiffness of 3D knitted fabric composites; the three knits HCP contain ramie and viscose fibres (w% means: weight percentage of matrix)

A second application required a combination of good ventilation and excellent shock absorbance. The influence of the pile composition and the matrix content on the deceleration during transverse impact is shown in fig. 22. The required maximum deceleration of 150 G can be met when using at least 3 layers of 3D-knitted fabric composites.

Fig. 22: Comparison between hexagonal and rhombic knitted composites and polysterene. Influence of the number of layers in the knitted composite. (Resin : 70w% Hexcel R2503)

In both aforementioned applications, the final form of the product had a complex three-dimensional shape. The high deformability of knitted fabrics allowed to realise these shapes without any problem.

CONCLUSIONS

Knitted fabrics have finally been discovered as an interesting alternative composite preform. The in-plane mechanical properties are reasonable compared to woven fabric composites, and superior to random mat composites. The out-of-plane properties (G_{Ic}) and damage tolerance are however better than most other composite preforms.

The major advantage remains the high deformability, which allows an efficient use in complex shaped composite products. A considerable decrease of processing costs can hence be envisaged. In resin transfer moulding applications, the excellent resin permeability is an additional processing advantage, allowing to impregnate large surfaces at low pressure in an acceptable time. In compression moulding applications of thermoplastic matrix composites, the extensional deformability of knitted fabrics makes the "organic sheets" behave like stampable metallic sheets.

It is however clear that the potential of knitted fabrics as preform for composites has not yet been fully exploited, and that the knitting technology is waiting for the imagination of composites engineers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Flemish government for their support of this research in the IWT-project "Optimalisatie van breisels voor composietstructuren". This text presents research results of the Belgian programme on Interuniversity Poles of Attraction initiated by the Belgian State, Prime Minister's Office, Science Policy Programming.

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